

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Study of Uranyl Complex with 1-Isonicotinoyl -2-Salicylidene Hydrazine (Salinazid)

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Uranyl ion forms a reddish brown, water soluble complex with 1-Isonicotinoyl-2-salicylidene hydrazine. The formula of the complex established spectrophotometrically and conductometrically is UO_2R ($R =$ Reagent). The apparent stability constant, $\log K$ at 36° has been found to be 4.2 and the free energy of formation -5.994 Kcal/mole. The complex ion in solution is cationic in nature.

Katiyar and Tandon¹ have described reactions of several metal ions with salinazid. This paper reports the results of spectrophotometric and conductometric studies of the reddish brown coloured complex formed when uranyl salt (at relatively low concentrations) reacts with alcoholic solution of salinazid. The colour is formed instantaneously and remains stable within the pH range 3.4 to 5.9 for about a week and shows an absorption maxima at $490 m\mu$, using ligand as a blank.

EXPERIMENTAL

A 0.01 M solution of uranyl acetate ($UO_2(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, B.D.H., A.R.) has been prepared by direct weighing and uranium contents estimated gravimetrically². Salinazid has been prepared by Sah and Peoples method³ and after purification its standard solution has been prepared by weighing and dissolving in 95% ethanol. The solution has been standardized by mercurimetric method⁴. A 0.1 M solution of potassium chloride B.D.H., A.R. has been used throughout the experiment for constant ionic concentration.

Spectrophotometric measurements are made with a Unicem SP1400 prism absorptiometer using a 10 mm. glass cell. The pH has been measured with a Beckman Zeromatic pH meter. The conductometric measurements are carried out with a Kohlrausch universal bridge (W. G. Pye Ltd.). The titration cell has been immersed in an electrically controlled thermostat, at a constant temperature of $36^\circ \pm 0.5$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The maximum colour formation is attained when the mixture contains greater than two fold excess of the reagent with respect to metal ion.

1. S. S. Katiyar and Tandon, *Talanta*, 1964, **11** (5), 892.
2. A. I. Vogel. "A Text book of quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1961, p. 539.
3. P. T. Sah and S. A. Peoples, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assn.*, 1954, **43**, 513.
4. A. Kulusheva and N. Nin'ova, *Farmatiya* (Sofia), 1960, **10**, 23.

The sensitivity of colour reactions as defined by Sandell⁵ (based on an absorbance of 0.001 units) for the metal ion was 0.096 r/cm². The Beer's law was obeyed in the wide concentration ranges of 6 to 60 p.p.m. of uranium. The molar extinction coefficient of the uranyl complex at 490 m μ has been found to be 800.

The composition 1 : 1 has been established spectrophotometrically with the help of Job's method of continued variation⁶ and mole ratio method⁷. All observations were taken at 4.0 pH and ionic strength 0.02 in 60% alcoholic medium. The total volume in each case was kept 10 ml. The composition has been further confirmed by conductometric titration method.

Calculation of stability constant : The stability of the complex has been calculated⁸ from the spectrophotometric data and the value of log K has been found to be 4.2 and the free energy of formation is -5.994 Kcal/mole at 36° from the equation $\Delta F = -RT \log K$.

Structure of complex : The pH meter has been calibrated⁹ and corrections applied in the reading for aqueous alcoholic mixtures. The pH value of uranyl salt solution of 0.005 M is 3.3 and that of salinazid of same concentration is 6.7, when the pH of the salinazid is lowered to 3.3 and the equal volume of the two were mixed, the pH becomes 2.7. This indicates an increase in $[H]^+$ ion concentration of the mixture, obviously due to liberation of $[H]^+$ from the phenolic hydroxyl group. Moreover, the complex in solution, when passed over cation exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120), is completely exchanged and later eluted by dilute acids. This indicated the cationic nature of the complex. Thus the tentative structure of the complex may be as follows :

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5. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals" 3rd ed. Interscience Publications, New York, 1965.
6. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.
7. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
8. A. K. Mukherji and A. K. Dey, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 461.
9. L. G. Van Uitert and C. G. Haas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.